

Case Report

Symmetrical Peripheral Gangrene, a Rare Complication of Unsafe Abortion: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

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Symmetrical peripheral gangrene is a rare condition seen in patients with severe sepsis and disseminated intravascular coagulopathy. Gangrene is of dry type, limited to the digits with all peripheral pulses palpable. A 39-year old admitted with septic abortion complicated by disseminated intravascular coagulopathy with symmetrical peripheral gangrene with background retro viral disease. She had deranged clotting profile, anaemia, elevated liver enzymes. She was managed with intravenous antibiotics, blood transfusion, low dose heparin. Patient continued to do well, gangrene was well demarcated, however she was lost to follow up. Symmetrical peripheral gangrene is a rare and devastating complication of sepsis. We present a rare case of symmetrical peripheral gangrene a complication of unsafe abortion to sensitize on the need for aggressive management of sepsis to prevent its occurrence in developing countries.

Keywords: Peripheral gangrene, Unsafe abortion, Sepsis, DIC

INTRODUCTION

Symmetrical peripheral gangrene (SPG) is a rare syndrome defined by a peripheral ischemic lesion of two or more extremities in the absence of major vascular obstructive disease¹. This was first described in 1891 by Hutchinson in a clinical case of sepsis with disseminated intravascular coagulopathy (DIC)². It is sometimes referred to as purpura fulminant which is an acute thrombotic disorder which manifest as blood spots, bruising and discolouration of the skin. It results from coagulation in small blood vessels within the skin and rapidly leads to skin necrosis and DIC³. It is a rare but severe complication of DIC that frequently accompanies sepsis⁴. Our patient had dry gangrene of the extremities following an unsafe abortion which is a rare occurrence.

CASE REPORT

Miss PJ was a 39-year-old, single who was P3+4 (3 alive). She presented with a 5-day history of severe lower abdominal pain, foul smelling vaginal discharge, fever and difficulty in breathing. Symptoms followed an unsafe surgical termination of a 12-week-old pregnancy because she was not married. She attained menarche at 14 years and menstruated for 4-6 days in a regular cycle of 28-30 days. She did not use any contraception.

She was a single lady and has had 3 spontaneous vaginal deliveries and 4 surgical termination of unwanted pregnancies. She was diagnosed with Retroviral disease 2 years prior to presentation and had been on highly active anti-retroviral therapy.

She was a young woman, acutely ill looking, in respiratory distress, lethargic, febrile (temp. 38°C) and pale with cold extremities. Her pulse rate was 132 beats/minute, blood pressure 80/(not recordable) mmHg. Respiratory rate was 48 cycles/minute, lung fields were clinically clear.

Abdomen was full and moved with respiration, there were generalized tenderness, guarding and rebound tenderness. Liver was 16cm below the right costal margin. The uterine size not assessed because of the level of tenderness and guarding. Normal vulva and vagina with foul smelling vaginal discharge. Marked cervical motion tenderness. Cervical os looked healthy and opened. Urethral catheter was passed to monitor urine output. An assessment of septic incomplete abortion in shock was made.

Her packed cell volume was 23% (low), urea 12.9 (elevated), creatinine 331 (elevated). Liver enzymes were elevated, AST 282 (<35), AL 64 (<45). Samples were taken for blood culture, High vaginal swab for M/C/S which yielded no growth. She was commenced on intravenous Ceftriaxone and Metronidazole. Two units of blood were grouped, crossmatched and transfused. She had abdomino-

pelvic ultrasound scan done which showed bulky uterus with retained products of conception. She had a manual vacuum aspiration done 24 hours after commencement of antibiotics.

On day 5 of admission patient was pale, had bilateral petechial and ecchymotic patches over the lower limbs and hyper-pigmented toes (figure 1). Both posterior tibia and dorsalis pedis arteries were palpable. An assessment of septic abortion complicated by disseminated intravascular coagulopathy with bilateral dry gangrene and background retro viral disease was made. Haematologist and orthopaedic surgeons were called to review.

The haematologist reviewed and made the same assessment with probably venous thrombo-embolism. samples were taken for PT, APTT, INR. PT-38.5s (9.5-13.5s), APTT-46.2s (30-40s), INR-3.13 (<1.1) (were all elevated). Blood film, chest X-ray and Doppler USS were normal. Packed cell volume was 20%. She was commenced on 3-5 litres of Oxygen by facemask, had 2 units of fresh whole blood transfused in the absence of fresh frozen plasma and subcutaneous enoxaparin 40mg 12 hourly. She made a steady recovery. The Orthopaedics team planned to see her in the clinic for surgical intervention after which the gangrene would have been well demarcated.

Doppler USS showed normal major arteries of both lower limbs with no sonographic evidence of DVT (figures 2a, 2b, 2c). The gangrene subsequently demarcates (figure 3a and b).

She was seen at the Orthopaedic clinic and counselled for Lisfranc amputation but she declined the procedure and was lost to follow up.

Figure 1:Hyperpigmented toes)

Figure 2c: Doppler of right popliteal artery)

Figure 2a:Doppler of left dorsalis pedis

Figure 3a: Gangrene demarcated

Figure 2b:Doppler of right Dorsalis artery

Figure 3b: Gangrene demarcated

DISCUSSION

Symmetrical Peripheral gangrene (SPG) is a rare syndrome defined by a peripheral ischemic lesion of two or more extremities in the absence of major vascular obstructive disease¹. Though rare is a scourging complication of septicaemia; most cases of SPG are associated with DIC⁵. Clinically, it may present with signs of ischemic limb injury, sharply demarcated and strikingly symmetrical that progresses rapidly to necrosis with palpable pulses⁶. As was noted in our patient. The pathogenesis of SPG is not well known. However, it is thought to be related to any condition which decreases the blood supply, and consequently the delivery of nutrients and oxygen to the more peripheral regions for an extended time⁷. Microcirculatory alterations, vasospastic conditions such as the use of vasoactive drugs, the state of low cardiac output are considered the most frequent associations with PSG.

Disseminated intravascular coagulopathy, often as a consequence of infection, appears to be frequently associated with SPG. Literature reports its occurrence in about 85% of cases⁷. Some authors believe DIC leads to ischemia and peripheral gangrene by formation of intravascular clots at the terminal vessels⁷, while others relate it to spasm of the peripheral vessels^{8,9}. Pathologic Examination of amputated specimens often reveals thrombi concentrated in the small vessels and not the large vessels⁸. Our patient had DIC following an unsafe abortion with associated uncontrolled sepsis.

The most frequently implicated microorganisms are pneumococcus, streptococcus and staphylococcus. However, cases of bacterial gram-negative infections, viral infections and infection by protozoa such as plasmodium falciparum have also been described^{10,11}. The offending organism in our patient could not be identified. This is most probably because our patient might have been on antibiotics before presentation.

The syndrome characteristically begins as erythematous or puerperal lesions. Gangrene is said to develop typically within 24-48hours of appearance of the herald lesion⁵. Dry gangrene developed after 5 days in this patient.

The goal of treatment of SPG is to halt the progression of the disease, to remove the causative factors, prevent secondary infection, correct hypovolemia and remove nonviable tissue³. Management is multidisciplinary approach involving internist, dermatologist, haematologist and orthopaedic surgeon³. In this patient, the haematologist and orthopaedic surgeon were involved.

Patient with SPG should be admitted and managed in intensive care unit³. However, at the time of managing our patient, intensive care unit was lacking in our facility. This necessitated admitting and managing her patient in the gynaecology ward. Shock from blood extravasation and sepsis requires extensive fluid replacement. The source of infection or precipitating factors should be sought and treated^{12,13}. In cases, where thrombosis is prominent as in the case presented, several anticoagulants can be used. Low dose of unfractionated heparin (300-500IU/hour) may be helpful to halt the progression of the pregangrenous changes to frank gangrene³. Low molecular weight heparin is found to be superior to unfractionated heparin¹⁴. This is because it has proven to improve the survival in patients with DIC. We used enoxaparin which is a low molecular weight heparin in our patient.

Treatment also entails protection and nursing care of the appendages, debridement of nonviable tissue should be carried out, however, early limb amputation should be avoided. Ample of time should be allowed to observed gangrene demarcation because it can be difficult to distinguish viable and non-viable tissue clinically¹³. The affected areas can be covered with skin graft¹⁴. Physiotherapy and other

efforts at restoring limb function should not be overlooked.

A high mortality rate of SPG (3 out of the 12 patients) has been reported in a recent retrospective case series¹⁶. A review of literature on SPG showed a mortality rate of 35%¹⁷. Mortality rate in a study in a tertiary-care hospital in eastern India was 5 out of 14 patients (35.7%) were also similar to these data¹⁵. Six patients out of the nine survivors in the study had amputations of some parts of the distal limbs (4 patients had auto-amputation and 2 patients underwent surgical amputation). A higher rate of amputation (8 of 9 survivors) was also previously reported¹⁶. Our patient declined amputation and further treatment due to probably cultural belief, ignorant of the fact that dead digits could be infected and could lead to death. She was lost to follow up.

CONCLUSION

Symmetrical peripheral gangrene is a rare, but devastating complication of sepsis and treatment is largely anecdotal^[15]. Clinicians are advised to prevent occurrence by managing all septic conditions aggressively. Early recognition of acrocyanosis, prompt management of DIC and underlying condition, haemodynamic stabilization, and properly controlled usage of anticoagulation may be helpful to halt the progression of pregangrenous stage to frank gangrene.

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